

ANALYSIS OF FAILURE IN TEXTILE COMPOSITES VIA MESO-DAMAGE MECHANICS

D.S. Ivanov, S.V. Lomov, K. Vallons, T. Troung Chi, I. Verpoest
Department of Materials Engineering, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
Kasteelpark Arenberg 44, B-3001, Leuven, Belgium
Dmitry.Ivanov@mtm.kuleuven.be

SUMMARY

Damage and failure of textile composites is modelled from perspective of internal architectures. The current study addresses to the non-linearity observed in the samples with dominated matrix deformation and failure. The new and robust concept includes a choice of minimum degraded entity, degradation scheme, definition of crack plane orientation, and a new damage evolution law. The latter is tested against known assumptions on post-critical behaviour of unidirectional (UD) ply. The model distinguishes between the non-linearity attributed to plasticity and to matrix intra-yarn cracking. Eventually, the results are verified against experimental analysis, which incorporates measurements of stiffness, local strain, damage initiation, damage induced stiffness degradation, and crack plane orientation. The modelling is illustrated on the examples of non-crimp fabric (NCF) and braided composites.

Keywords: textile composites, damage mechanics, stiffness degradation, failure

INTRODUCTION

The failure of textile composites is complicated multi-scale process exhibiting various failure modes. Internal architecture and type of loading govern all the aspects of the damage accumulation: damage initiation, non-linearity induced by damage, crack density, crack types/modes, stability of the damage accumulation, toughness and failure mode. Textile composites exhibit several particular features that are not observed for other composites such as non-crimp UD laminates. In particular, these are earlier crack initiation, stable matrix crack propagation, competing mechanisms of crack propagation and crack density increase [1, 2].

The concept of the current study is to perform failure analysis at the meso-scale, where geometry of yarns and matrix rich zones is distinguished. It allows analysing various textile architectures by the same approach with the same input data. The data is coming from experiments on matrix, UD and UD-laminated composites. In this study the modelling is illustrated on examples of carbon-epoxy non-crimp fabric (NCF) and braided composites produced with the same matrix and under the same manufacturing parameters.

To avoid the fundamental paradoxes of local damage mechanics [3], an alternative modelling direction is proposed. A continuous damage mechanics approach is applied to every yarn segment, defined as a volume between two neighbouring yarn cross-sections, which are made perpendicular to the yarn mid-line. Hence, within every segment the

orientation of the coordinate system is constant, which is consistent with the intention to use the theory developed for the flat UD plies. Once the meso stress distribution is obtained, it is averaged inside the segments, and the average values govern the segment degradation.

Damage mechanics models can be subdivided to two groups: based on mechanical assumptions and those found on dissipative energy or energy release rate (ERR) functions. The latter, stating that no restoration of the dissipated energy is possible, establish a material law in which the ERR is associated with the damage variable(s). Material constants for this law can be either found by fitting experimental diagrams obtained in a cyclic loading – unloading tensile test [4,5], or by an inverse numerical-experimental study of a dissipative energy in specimens with stress concentrators [6]. Experimental study of textile composites with various architectures has revealed that the emission of the acoustic emission energy directly correlates both with the density of intra-yarn matrix cracks and with the stiffness degradation [2]. For this reason, the models based on the ERR seem to be attractive in application to textile composites modelling.

The mechanical approaches allude to the assumption that certain stress-strain (or the stress-strain invariants) diagrams can be treated as material property, e.g. in the model of Zinoviev et.al. [7]. The relation of shear stress and strain is considered to remain the same for both the situations of a complex deformation or a pure shear test. The mechanical models require less experimental input than the ERR models and they have been validated by the World-Wide Failure Exercise [8]. However, depending on the

Figure 1. Tensile tests for biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF composites with a brittle (^b) and tough matrices (^t). Tests are performed along (MD) and across (CD) the stitching direction. The onset of intra-ply matrix cracking starts at $\sim 1.0 - 1.3$ % of the applied deformation.

used matrix, these assumptions can describe well one carbon-epoxy system and be very far from reality for another one - Figure 1. Hence, a constructed model needs to be flexible for adjusting to the different UD-ply behaviour.

Both the mechanical and the ERR models have the same key issues concerning the post-critical stage, that is absence of direct measurements for definition of the material law parameters. Neither diagram on the post-critical stage, nor damage-energy function can be directly obtained from tests on UD composite, because the bearing capacity of one cracked ply is provided by

the adjacent material.

In the current study, the tensile test on NCF composite of biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ configuration is used to extract the properties of UD composite on the basis of inverse FE procedure. Consequently, the obtained material law is applied for the other configurations and validated. A damage evolution model is constructed through ERR function, the one-parameter degradation scheme and micro mechanical considerations. The validity of the model will be checked by comparing with the degradation scheme of Zinoviev.

DAMAGE DEGRADATION SCHEME

The deterioration of the stiffness is caused by the two interrelated factors: (1) the opening of the crack faces, and (2) unloading of a volume in crack neighbourhood, which does not participate in the deformation of the material. At a certain distance from the crack, the stress rebuilds. However, the “healthy” load bearing volume is reduced in size and the total effective stiffness over the volume with the unloaded regions drops down. In the approach of Murakami [9], a similar reasoning stands behind the anisotropic tensorial stiffness degradation scheme. Three damage parameters are introduced as area fractions of the defect in projections to the coordinate planes. For the case of a ply in the composite, a defect should be imagined not as a mathematical cut, but rather as the volume in the crack vicinity where the stress is released. The second rank damage tensor is then introduced as:

$$\mathbf{D} = \sum_i d_i \mathbf{n}_i \otimes \mathbf{n}_i \quad [\mathbf{D}] = \begin{bmatrix} d_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where d_i and \vec{n} are the principal values and principal unit vector of the damage tensor. As it is declared in [9], only the diagonal components are meaningful within the given geometrical interpretations. If the crack plane is predefined, e.g. 1-3, only one of these components, d_2 , has a non zero magnitude. The search for the crack plane can be done by means of the Mohr-Hashin-Puck theory [10]. The energy equivalence of the damaged and the equivalent homogenous damaged media leads to the definition of the degraded material stiffness matrix [11].

The damage parameter influences both transverse and shear moduli reduction. Due to the symmetrisation of the effective stress tensor, the following reduction of the engineering constants takes place: $E_2 = E_2^0(1-d_2)^2$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{12}^0(1-d_2)$, $\nu_{23} = \nu_{23}^0(1-d_2)$, where index 0 corresponds to intact material, coordinate ‘1’ denotes the fibre direction. Hence, comparison of the degraded shear modulus, introduced as $G_{12} = G_{12}^0(1-d_{12})$, provides the link between the parameters d_2 and d_{12} :

$$d_2 = \frac{2(1-\sqrt{1-d_{12}})}{(2-\sqrt{1-d_{12}})} \quad (2)$$

The damage factors d_2 and d_{12} are nearly proportional, especially at small values. It is important to emphasise that this reduction scheme differs from those presented in many theories developed for UD laminated composites. The degradation scheme of Murakami predicts stronger reduction of the E-modulus than the one of the shear modulus (for example reduction of the shear modulus 2 times corresponds to factor 4 drop of the E-modulus). This is a consequence of the symmetrisation of effective stress in the reference homogeneous medium with the degraded properties.

There are non-direct observations in favour of “non-equality” of these damage parameters. In the WWFE, one of the most challenging cases (where all the predictions are far from reality) is biaxial loading ($\sigma_y : \sigma_x = 2 : 1$) of $\pm 55^\circ$ glass-epoxy composites. Puck and Schurmann [12] discuss the deviation of the predicted and experimental

diagrams as following: “*The unplausible predictions possibly resulting from the degradation method for inter-fibre failure of Mode A¹. It can easily be corrected by using a higher degradation-rate for the E-modulus than for the in-plane shear modulus*”.

DAMAGE EVOLUTION LAW

Elastic energy of the damaged UD ply is chosen with respect to the Murakami degradation scheme:

$$\Psi = \frac{1}{2} \left[\begin{aligned} & \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{E_1^0} + \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{E_2^0(1-d_2)^2} + \frac{\sigma_{33}^2}{E_3^0} - \\ & \frac{2\nu_{21}^0\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22}}{E_2^0(1-d_2)} - \frac{2\nu_{23}^0\sigma_{33}\sigma_{22}}{E_2^0(1-d_2)} - \frac{2\nu_{13}^0\sigma_{11}\sigma_{33}}{E_1^0} + \\ & + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{G_{12}^0(1-d_{12})} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{G_{23}^0(1-d_{12})} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{G_{13}^0} \end{aligned} \right] \quad (3)$$

It is postulated that all the cracks have the same orientation, which is often confirmed by cross-sectioning.

Damage parameters in (3) are associated only with the meso intra-yarn cracking. It is implied that once a critical stress in the fibre direction is achieved it causes catastrophic fibre rupture and failure of composite. The damage induced by micro cracking and plasticity will be introduced later.

Following the continuum damage models [4], we employ the ERR Y_{12} , also known as damage fictitious force, as a characteristic driving the damage accumulation. Conventionally, it is introduced as the square root of derivative of the elastic energy of the damaged material Ψ with respect to the degradation parameter:

$$Y_{12} = \sqrt{\text{Sup}_{\tau \leq t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial d_{12}} \Psi \right)} \quad (4)$$

where operator $\text{Sup}_{\tau \leq t}(\dots)$ denotes the maximum over the time period t and reflects the fact that the damage state is non-healing. As a result of the differentiating (4), the energy ERR turns to be dependent not only on the shear stress τ_{12} , but also on the longitudinal stress σ_{11} , the transverse stress σ_{22} and out-of plane shear stress τ_{23} .

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial d_{12}} = \frac{1}{E_2^0(1-d_2)^2} \frac{\partial d_2}{\partial d_{12}} \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{(1-d_2)} - (\nu_{21}^0\sigma_{11} + \nu_{23}^0\sigma_{33}) \right) + \frac{1}{2(1-d_{12})^2} \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^2}{G_{12}^0} + \frac{\tau_{23}^2}{G_{23}^0} \right) \quad (5)$$

Or in the strain-form, which is more convenient when modelling the post-critical stage:

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial d_{12}} = \frac{\partial d_2}{\partial d_{12}} (1-d_2) \epsilon_{22} (\epsilon_{22} C_{22}^0 (1-d_2) + \epsilon_{11} C_{12}^0 + \epsilon_{33} C_{13}^0) + \frac{1}{2} (G_{12}^0 (\gamma_{12}^e)^2 + G_{23}^0 (\gamma_{23}^e)^2) \quad (6)$$

¹ when there is a tensile stress normal to the crack faces and the crack is ‘open’

where d_2 is defined above in equation (2) and the derivative of the damage parameter is obtained consequently on basis of that definition, $\gamma_{12}^e = \gamma_{12} - \gamma_{12}^\mu$, $\gamma_{23}^e = \gamma_{23} - \gamma_{23}^\mu$ and γ_{12}^μ , γ_{23}^μ - are the accumulated plastic shear deformation in planes 1-2 and 2-3. The micro effects, as detected in experiments, are assumed to have small influence on the normal strain components. The shear damage degradation factor is defined with respect to the irreversible deformations: $d_{12} = 1 - \tau_{12} / (\gamma_{12}^e G_{12}^0)$.

The chosen degradation scheme is not compatible with this form of damage evolution law, which is supposed to be invariant to loading conditions. Only one damage parameter is independent and hence, only one master function governs the degradation rate. However, the ERR at damage onset is different in a pure shear or a transverse tension or a mixed deformation mode.

At the moment of failure onset all the damage parameters are practically close to zero $d_2 = 0$, $d_{12} = 0$, otherwise it results in a discontinuity of a stress-strain diagram. The derivative of the damage parameter is $\partial d_2 / \partial d_{12} = 1$. Consider a loading, which is realised in the state of a pure transverse tension in the direction x_2 . The transverse Poisson's contraction is expressed in the strains $\epsilon_{11} = -\nu_{21} \epsilon_{22}^{cr}$ and $\epsilon_{33} = -\nu_{23} \epsilon_{22}^{cr}$, where ϵ_{22}^{cr} - is the strain at failure of the UD composite. Exploiting the definition of ERR (6) and accounting that $E_2^0 = C_{22}^0 - \nu_{12} C_{12}^0 - \nu_{13} C_{13}^0$, we get $Y_{12}^{tension} = \epsilon_{22}^{cr} \sqrt{2E_2^0}$. Analogical derivation holds for the instance of the pure shear, where cracking starts at the ERR $Y_{12}^{shear} = \gamma_{12}^{cr} \sqrt{G_{12}^0}$. It is clear that these two values are not necessarily equal $Y_{12}^{shear} \neq Y_{12}^{tension}$. This contradiction can be handled through the normalisation of damage evolution law argument by the ERR Y_{12}^0 calculated at the moment of damage initiation:

$$d_{12}^{cr} = d_{12}^{cr} \left(\frac{Y_{12}}{Y_{12}^0} \right) \quad (7)$$

POST-FAILURE ASSUMPTIONS

Test problem

The proposed model corresponds to the well-known assumptions about the post-critical behaviour of UD ply by Zinoviev, which proved to be valid in the World-Wide Failure Exercise [7]. Once the existence of the master curve is assumed, this function is suggested to be invariant to the loading conditions. In what follows the assumed shear stress-strain diagram of Zinoviev is recalculated to the damage evolution law. Then, using this damage evolution law the stress-

Figure 2. Comparison of the damage evolution laws: (a) shear diagram, (b) transverse tension diagram; Z - assumed by Zinoviev et.al. [7], I - obtained in the current work. The properties of carbon-fibre composite are used.

strain diagram of transverse tension test is built and compared with the second assumption about the behaviour of transverse stress-strain curve. In these instances it can be demonstrated whether the proposed model is far or close to the other successful predictions.

Consider the shear diagram - Figure 2a. The stress is linear up to the failure onset at stress level τ_{12}^{cr} . Then the stress level, τ_{12}^{cr} , remains constant with the increase of the deformation. To write the damage evolution law, the definition of ERR (5) is used. Energy release rate at this “plateau” is written as:

$$\bar{Y}_{12} = \frac{\tau_{12}^{cr}}{(1-d_{12})} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2G_{12}^0}} \quad (8)$$

Consequently, the damage parameter is expressed as a function of the ERR in pure shear \bar{Y}_{12} loading.

$$d_{12} = 1 - \frac{\bar{Y}_{12}^0}{\bar{Y}_{12}} \quad (9)$$

Since the damage evolution law is invariant to the loading situation, based on (9) we can obtain the diagram of pure transverse tension. To construct it, the ERR for pure transverse tension \hat{Y}_{12} and the ERR at damage onset \hat{Y}_{12}^0 by means of equation (6) are substituted to the damage evolution law (9) postulating that conditions of pure shear and pure transverse tension are related $\frac{\hat{Y}_{12}}{\hat{Y}_{12}^0} = \frac{\bar{Y}_{12}}{\bar{Y}_{12}^0}$. It results in a non-linear equation with

respect to the damage parameter d_{12} . Note that d_2 and $\partial d_2 / \partial d_{12}$ are considered as functions of d_{12} as follows from the degradation scheme. This point has to be emphasized: the shear degradation is present (along with the degradation of the transverse modulus) even in the case of pure tensile load of UD composite. Physically it means that if the tensile test is stopped at an advanced stage of the damage accumulation and then the damaged composite is loaded in pure shear, then it would exhibit a degradation of the instant shear modulus in comparison with the intact material.

After solving the equation, the transverse degradation parameter d_2 is calculated as a function of the applied strain. Hence, the stress-strain diagram can be obtained point by point. Figure 2b eloquently shows a good match with the second assumption of Zinoviev. For the instance of brittle matrix [13], as shown in Figure 1, the $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF composites with the stiffened epoxy, the damage evolution law will be better described by a step-

$$\text{wise function: } d = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } Y/Y^0 < 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } Y/Y^0 \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

Damage evolution in UD fibre bundle

The master curves of the damage material law are extracted from the tensile test of biaxial non-crimp fabric $\pm 45^\circ$ composites in an inverse FE procedure. The shear degradation of the UD plies is adjusted so as to fit the experimental diagram, accounting for geometry of the composites, fibre reorientation, evolution of the elastic constants,

transverse and shear degradation, failure initiation and non-linearity of the matrix in the resin rich zones. The ply behaviour is extracted from tensile test on composites with fibre volume fractions 22 % and 39 %.

Figure 3. FE models of NCF composites

The FE model is found on a simplified representation of the geometry - Figure 3 [14]. The out-of plane crimp/waviness of the plies is neglected. The stitching yarns are excluded for simplicity:

their stiffness contribution is close to the one of the matrix. The effect of the stitching is accounted for by introducing matrix resin rich zones of proper dimensions at the stitching sites. The distortions imposed by stitching cause local variation of orientation and volume fraction of the fibres. The orientation of the coordinate system is introduced as a linear function of the distance from the distortion boundaries. The “disturbed” area width is of the same size as the local distortion width.

A peculiar feature of the obtained diagram is that the composite with higher fibre volume fraction exhibits much higher toughness and strain to failure. This can be explained by the fact that crack density is higher for the composites with higher fibre volume fraction. The micro mechanics of this process is out of the scope of the current research, however it can be suggested that when the fibres are packed more closely it takes less space, an ‘effective length’, to rebuild the stress aside from the crack. The less is the effective cracked zone, the more energy can the material accommodate. It is worth mentioning that the failure strain of the epoxy matrix subjected to shear (estimated from the tensile test based on von Mises assumptions) is lower than the strain to failure of the UD composites with both of the fibre volume fractions. Thus, the trend is explicit: the higher fibre volume fraction makes the composite more tough for the reason of more intensive matrix cracking.

Figure 4. Shear diagrams “extracted” from two tensile tests with different total fibre volume fraction of biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF composites via inverse FE procedure; V_f denotes fibre volume fractions. $V_f = 0.273$, 0.244 relates to the upper and bottom plies in experiment with total $V_f = 0.22$, $V_f = 0.475$, 0.425 relates to another experiment with total $V_f = 0.39$; b) Test $\pm 60^\circ$ NCF composites and correspondent FE model.

The experiments on $\pm 60^\circ$ NCF composites show that the assumption of slow growing stress on the post-critical tensile diagram is meaningful. The assumption about the plateau on the shear diagram also describes the reality quite well. The tensile test on $\pm 60^\circ$ NCF composites, where the transverse stress is dominated, exhibits a linear behaviour up to the failure initiation and then a post-critical plateau, like the one

assumed in the model of Zinoviev [7] - Figure 4b. This proves the validity of the model and, in absence of experimental data, the damage evolution law (9) can be used.

A different behaviour is observed in the tests on $\pm 70^\circ$ NCF composites - Figure 5c. Due to the high angle between the fibre and loading directions, the adjacent ply are too weak to support post-critical deformation of each other and hence, the composite fails soon after the damage initiation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NCF composites;

The tests on $\pm 60^\circ$ composite exhibit a good correspondence with experiments - Figure 4b. It is almost linear before the meso-damage initiation. At the stage of the transverse cracking, it has slightly overestimated the stress.

Figure 5. a) Normalised secant moduli E_{sec} in the tensile tests of NCF composites. Figure represents only the non-linearity associated with plasticity but not the final failure. b) The tensile diagram of $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF, fibre volume fraction c) Tensile test of the NCF $\pm 60^\circ$ composite. Experiment (Exp) vs. FE analysis (FEA).

Figure 5a shows an adequate prediction of the non-linearity attributed to the pre-cracking, plastic shear deformations. The transverse degradation is not “switched on” owing to the earlier fibre failure. Both the plasticity and intensive intra-yarn cracking are present in $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test Figure 5b. The crack onset is predicted at 1.23 % of applied deformation against the experimentally determined value 1.3 %. On Figure 5c modelling results of $\pm 70^\circ$ NCF composite are displayed. The model is not capable to predict the sudden drop of the stress after the damage initiation on account of the neglecting the effects of adjacent plies stiffness. Instead, it predicts a similar curve to the instance of $\pm 60^\circ$ NCF composites.

Figure 6 Tensile test of the braided composite: comparison of the experiment (Exp) with the modelling results. “FEA-per” stands for FE analysis with periodic out-of-plane boundary conditions, “FEA-sym” is analysis with the symmetric out-of-plane boundary conditions;

The triaxial braided composite [1, 3] has been tested in cross non-fibre direction, so that the braiding yarns are oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the loading direction and inlay yarns is at 90° . The geometrical model has been produced using the geometrical pre-processor WiseTex [15]. Solid and finite element model has been created by adopting this geometrical model through an

Braided composite

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additional mechanical processing [3].

The modelling of the braided composite is carried out both under symmetric and periodic out-of-plane boundary conditions. Modelled tensile diagram of the test in the matrix dominated cross-fibre direction is compared with the experimental data in Figure 6. The periodic boundary conditions show a good match with the experiments, while the modelling with the symmetric boundary conditions leads to 30 % overestimation of stress at the critical strain 1.1 %. Note that the employed model does not predict the composite strength for the failure mechanisms are primary stipulated by the delaminations, which are not yet accounted in the presented model. Stiffer response of the symmetric laminate is conditioned by the constraints on the upper and the bottom boundaries of the unit cell. The periodic conditions lead to large out-of-plane displacement. The less constrained structure deforms freely and it exhibits a lower resistance.

The mechanism of the damage accumulation, generally similar for both the configurations. Prior to damage onset there is the non-linearity associated with the plasticity/micro cracking. The meso cracking starts with failure of the inlay yarns, and soon proceeds with the cracking of the braiding yarns. It initiates at the locations where the yarns are oriented out-of the plane of the textile, that is when the horizontal yarn dives under the vertical braiding yarn - location $B_1^<$ as pointed in Figure 7c, and the vertical braiding yarn dives under the inlay yarn - location $B_2^<$. The most probable failure planes at these locations are rotated under an angle of 20° to the plane of the textile around the fibre axis Figure 7a,b. The micrographs of the damaged samples show nearly the same orientation as predicted by FE model. After degradation of these segments, the damage spreads over the braiding yarns. However, even at the critical strain level, where the real samples fail (1.1 %), the model shows segment which are not damaged at all.

Figure 7 i) The damage evolution d_2 in the tensile test in the cross-direction (x -axis) at 3 stages: (1) onset of inlay yarn cracking, (2) onset of the braiding yarn cracking, (3) the critical load level. ii-a) Rotation of the initial coordinate system $y-z$ around the fibre axis x at the angle $\theta=20^\circ$ towards the most probable failure plane $y'-z'$ at the location $B_1^<$; ii-b) micro graphs of a damaged CD sample;

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed damage evolution law has deliberately been kept as simple as possible. The degradation scheme of Murakami along with determining of the failure plane allows having only one damage parameter. Using the segment as the basic damage entity promotes the modelling of parallel mechanisms between the degradation of the current segment (increase of the number of the cracks) or the space-wise evolution of degradation to the next segment (increase of the length of the existent crack).

The meso-scale approach shows good potential in predicting of the stiffness degradation and the final failure. The internal distribution of the damage parameter allows seeing an effect of scissoring one braiding yarn in between the inlay yarn and the braiding yarn of another direction. The verification for the braided and NCF composites of various configurations covers a good range of the composite internal strain states.

The propagation of the delamination has not yet been accounted here. It can be assumed that due the orientation of inter-yarn cracks, there contribution to the stiffness change is not critical. However, for predictions of the final failure the correct modelling of the delamination is important.

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